

Human Skin Disease Detection Using CNN

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Abstract— Skin, as the outermost integument of the human body, plays a significant role in protecting our bodies from sunlight, cold, and various harmful germs and materials. Human skin types vary from person to person, providing a diverse habitat for microorganisms and bacteria. Sometimes, abnormalities in the skin can also manifest as significant symptoms of underlying diseases. Therefore, it is essential to detect and accurately diagnose skin diseases in their early stages to prevent the spread of the disease. Our project involves image processing and classification of skin diseases using image data, implemented with the assistance of classifiers such as Convolutional Neural Networks, TensorFlow and Mobile Net in the domain of Deep Learning. Consequently, this project serves as an early warning system, informing users about skin diseases they may be experiencing through computer-aided methods. To implement model, we gathered approximately 2102 image datasets from a massive repository of diverse source images, particularly dermatoscopic images of pigmented lesions. Our experiment results show an 89.45 percent accuracy in detecting skin cancer disease. We hope our proposed method will help to diagnose this skin cancer disease more efficient way than other methods that have already been used

Keywords— Skin diseases, deep learning, convolutional neural network (CNN)

I. INTRODUCTION

Skin conditions can arise from many factors, including fungi, bacteria, allergic reactions, and microbial activity, often leading to chronic conditions and potentially cancerous tissue if left untreated. Due to the various manifestations of skin disorders and the shortage of dermatologists, data-based diagnostics have become a necessity. Advances in lasers and photonics-based medical technologies have enabled faster and more accurate identification of these conditions. However, the high cost of treatment is a barrier to access, especially in low-income regions. Automated dermatological screening systems using image processing algorithms have been developed to address these issues. Computer vision techniques, including artificial neural networks (ANNs) and convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have shown promise in skin disease detection, although CNN models can struggle with scale and rotation invariance, limiting their applicability to smartphone images or digital cameras. However, the advent of deep learning algorithms, driven by the abundance of data and increased computing power, has the potential to achieve human-level performance in a variety of domains. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have made significant advances in the field of medical image processing, particularly

for pathology, CT, and MRI images with stiff characteristics and high resolution, Finally the

are shown to the user, including the type of disease, spread, and severity. The system successfully detects 3 different types of skin diseases with an accuracy

II. RELATED WORKS

- A. The study titled " Skin Disease Detection and Classification" [1] Skin acts as the body's frontline defense, shielding against sunlight, cold, and harmful substances, while a harboring various microorganisms. Differences in skin types can indicate underlying health issues through visible signs. Early detection and diagnosis of skin diseases are essential for containment. Our project utilizes image processing and classification techniques, harnessing Convolutional Neural Networks and MobileNet in Deep Learning. As an early warning system, it aids users in precisely identifying skin diseases through computer-aided methods.
- B. In " A Decision Machine Learning Support System for" [2] machine learning models with modern deep learning approaches using various metrics for skin disease classification. Therefore, this paper introduces a Decision Machine Learning Support System for Human Skin Disease Classifier (DSSC), focusing on classifying five skin disease classes with 750 images from the Dermnet dataset. The proposed system involves image preprocessing, resizing, interpolation, and augmentation to prepare input images for all models. Extensive experiments reveal that ResNet50 significantly outperforms other methods in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F-measure.
- C. Another relevant contribution is the study on " Human Skin Diseases Detection and Classification using CNN"[3] In recent years, automated computer vision and artificial neural network-based approaches have emerged as promising alternatives for skin disease detection, offering improved accuracy in prediction. In this study, we propose a deep learning-based Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) method for classifying skin diseases, leveraging a dataset of 2102 images sourced from diverse repositories, especially dermatoscopic images of pigmented lesions. Our experimental results demonstrate an accuracy of 89.45% in detecting skin cancer disease, showcasing the potential of our proposed method to enhance the efficiency of skin cancer diagnosis compared to existing approaches.

- D. Lastly, the study on “Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for Image Detection and Recognition” [4] Deep learning algorithms, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), are modeled after the human brain's cortex and consist of many hidden layers. CNNs, specifically, are adept at processing large datasets, particularly 2D images, by convolving them with filters to produce desired outputs. In this study, CNN models were constructed and evaluated for image recognition and detection tasks using the MNIST and CIFAR-10 datasets. The models achieved an accuracy of 99.6% on MNIST and utilized real-time data augmentation and dropout techniques to improve performance on CIFAR-10.
- E. “Automated skin disease identification using deep learning algorithms [5] utilised different Deep Learning algorithms (Inceptionv3, MobileNet, Resnet, Xception) for feature extraction and Logistic Regression as a learning technique for training and testing. Using ensemble feature mapping, a voting-based model was then ensemble, boosting the effectiveness.
- F. “Targeted Ensemble Machine Classification Approach for Supporting IoT Enabled Skin Disease Detection [6] presented a two-phase "Targeting Ensemble Machine Classify Model (TEMPM)" strategy to produce the best result from the remaining models as part of a novel classification procedure to produce improved classification results in skin disease detection. The evaluation tested alternative combinations of the three pre-processing techniques—color featuring, model transfer, and data balancing—that worked on the condition photos using only Keras (a neural network library) GPU APIs.
- G. "Diagnosis of skin diseases using Convolutional Neural Networks “[7] provided a system that categorised the image based on the method of the softmax classifier and extracted the diagnosis report as an output by performing feature extraction utilising sophisticated techniques like Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)
- H. A method of skin disease detection using image [8] provided a system that categorised the processing and machine learning proposed a system for detection, extraction and classification of skin disease using pre-trained convolutional neural network (AlexNet) and SVM. AlexNet consists of five convolutional layers, where a nonlinear RELU layer was stacked after each convolutional layer. In addition, the first, second, and fifth layers contain max pooling layers. After the feature extraction was done the classification was done by Support Vector Machine.

III. MOTIVATION

"Skin Disease Detection Using CNN" stems from a deeply-rooted passion for leveraging technology to address pressing healthcare challenges. Skin diseases affect millions worldwide, often causing discomfort, stigma, and in severe

cases, life-threatening complications. By delving into the realm of convolutional neural networks (CNNs), renowned for their prowess in image recognition and analysis, we aim to revolutionize the diagnosis and management of skin conditions. One unique aspect of our approach is the integration of an innovative feature: the translation of diagnostic outputs into accessible audio format. This adaptation holds immense potential in enhancing accessibility for visually impaired individuals, empowering them with timely and accurate health information. Moreover, by bridging the gap between cutting-edge technology and inclusive healthcare solutions, our endeavour aligns with the principles of equity and social responsibility. Through this seminar, I aspire to not only showcase the capabilities of CNNs in healthcare but also to catalyse discussions on how technology can be harnessed to foster a more inclusive and equitable society.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology includes using image processing algorithms and computer vision technology, including artificial neural networks (ANN) and convolutional neural networks (CNN), to automate dermatology screening. These techniques allow for the analysis of skin images to identify different skin conditions. Despite the advantages, challenges like addressing scaling and rotation issues in CNN models may require additional fine-tuning to make them more effective for a range of image sources, like digital camera images.

A. Data Collection: Data collection is a process of collecting the data in different source Prepare the dataset in 1145 images of Disease. The various 7 Class are present in the dataset that are:

Figure 1 Cellulitis Images

B. Data Pre-processing: Data Pre-processing is resize the images into fixed size. Preparing data for analysis by removing or modifying data that is incorrect, incomplete, irrelevant, duplicated, or improperly formatted

C. Grey-scale conversion: The obtained image is converted to black and white, eliminating hue and saturation information while retaining luminance.

D. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs):

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a class of deep learning algorithms specifically designed for processing structured grid data, such as images. The fundamental operation in a CNN is convolution, which involves applying a series of learnable filters (kernels) to input images to extract features. Mathematically, convolution can be represented CNNs consist of multiple layers, including convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers. Convolutional layers apply convolution operations to extract features, while pooling layers downsample the feature maps to reduce computational complexity and extract dominant features. Fully connected layers integrate the extracted features for classification or regression tasks. In summary, CNNs leverage convolution operations and deep architectures to automatically learn hierarchical features from input data, making them powerful tools for image processing and analysis.

V. BUILD MODEL

1. Import the packages that are necessary

```
import streamlit as st
from tensorflow.keras.models import load_model
import numpy as np
import cv2
from gtts import gTTS
from googletrans import Translator
import os
```

2. Read and resize the test image.

```
# Function to preprocess the input image
def preprocess_image(image):
    # Resize the image to match the input size of the model
    resized_image = cv2.resize(image, (224, 224))
    # Normalize the image
    normalized_image = resized_image / 255.0
    # Add batch dimension
    input_image = np.expand_dims(normalized_image, axis=0)
    return input_image
```

3. Function to Detect :

The function called detect is designed to generate predictions using a pre-trained model. It begins by verifying whether the dimensions of the input image meet the required size (224x224 pixels with 3 color channels). If the dimensions are appropriate, the image undergoes preprocessing using the preprocess_image function. Subsequently, the pre-trained model is utilized to make predictions on the preprocessed image. If the highest confidence score in the detection falls below a designated threshold (default value: 0.5), the function outputs None, indicating uncertainty. Conversely, if the confidence score surpasses the threshold, the function outputs the prediction, offering insights into the potential skin disease class depicted in the input image.

```
# Function to make detections
def detect(image, model, threshold=0.5):
    # Check if image dimensions are within the expected range
    if image.shape != (224, 224, 3):
        return None
    # Preprocess the input image
    processed_image = preprocess_image(image)
    # Make detection
    detect = model.predict(processed_image)
    # Check if detection confidence is below threshold
    if np.max(detect) < threshold:
        return None
    else:
        return detect
```

4. Process of Detection in CNN:

The process commences with the conversion of the uploaded image file into a NumPy array of unsigned 8-bit integers, achieved by interpreting it as a binary string using np.fromstring(). This array undergoes decoding into an image format through the utilization of cv2.imdecode() in its original color format, denoted by the parameter 1. The subsequent step involves assessing whether the resulting image conforms to RGB format criteria, ensuring it possesses three dimensions with the third-dimension indicative of the color channels being of size 3. Upon meeting these prerequisites, the image is showcased to the user. Following this, a prediction regarding the skin disease is generated using a pretrained model. In instances where the prediction's confidence level dips below a predefined threshold, the application notifies the user of its inability to ascertain the disease definitively. Conversely, when the confidence level surpasses the threshold, the application presents the predicted skin disease class, thus furnishing the user with valuable insights into the possible condition of their skin lesion.

```
if uploaded_file is not None:
    image = cv2.imdecode(np.fromstring(uploaded_file.read(), np.uint8),
    # Check if image is in RGB format
    if image is not None and len(image.shape) == 3 and image.shape[2] :
        # Display the uploaded image
        st.image(image, caption='Uploaded Image', use_column_width=True

        # Make prediction
        prediction = predict(image, model)

        if prediction is None:
            st.write("Sorry, cannot identify.")
        else:
            disease_classes = ['cellulitis', 'impetigo', 'athlete-foot']
            predicted_class_index = np.argmax(prediction)
```

valuable insights into skin disease detection while accommodating users' language preferences.

V.RESULT

Skin Disease Detection

Upload an image of the skin lesion to predict the disease.

Choose an image...

Drag and drop file here
Limit 200MB per file • JPG, PNG, JPEG

Browse files

Select Language for Translation:

English

5.Text Translate:

the application employs the Google Translate API through the googletrans library. This allows the translation of relevant text, such as product information, into the selected language. Utilizing the destination language specified by the user, the translator instance translates the text accordingly.

```
# Translate to the selected language
translator = Translator()
translated_text = translator.translate(product_info, dest=languages[selected_language]).text
```

6.Translate Text to Audio:

Incorporating text-to-speech functionality into the application, the code segment utilizes the gTTS library to convert translated product information into audio format. After translation, the text is passed to gTTS, which generates an audio file in the selected language. This audio file is then presented to the user using Streamlit's st.audio function, enabling them to listen to the product information in their preferred language. This feature enhances accessibility and user engagement by providing alternative modes of content consumption, catering to individuals with different preferences or accessibility needs.

```
# Text-to-speech conversion for each translated product info
tts_product_info = gTTS(text=translated_text, lang=languages[selected_language])
tts_product_info.save("product_info.mp3")
audio_file_product_info = open("product_info.mp3", 'rb')
audio_bytes_product_info = audio_file_product_info.read()
st.audio(audio_bytes_product_info, format='audio/mp3', start_time=0)
```

Figure 2. Input User Interface

Figure 4. Input Image

Your skin lesion appears to be cutaneous-larva-migrans.

Recommended product(s):

Prescription-strength antiparasitic medications.

From image preprocessing to prediction and language translation, each step is meticulously designed to provide

Figure 5. Output Image

Figure 6. Plot Scatter

VI. CONCLUSION

In summary, the integration of cutting-edge image processing techniques and machine learning algorithms significantly bolsters the performance and accuracy of skin disease detection. This integration empowers users with precise predictions and tailored recommendations, thus amplifying the effectiveness of disease management. Moreover, the inclusion of multilingual support and text-to-speech capabilities caters to diverse user needs, fostering inclusivity and enhancing user engagement. This holistic approach underscores the application's dedication to providing accessible and user-friendly solutions for skin disease detection and management. Through its emphasis on performance, accuracy, and user-centric design, the application emerges as a formidable platform for effective diagnosis and intervention in skin health.

VII. REFERENCES

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